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V2X Security within the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox

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Our greatest weakness lies in giving up.

The most certain way to succeed is always to try just one more time.

– Thomas Edison

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Abstract

This thesis deals with the integration and demonstration of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) security components within the Vehicle Communication Platform to Anything (vehicleCAPTAIN) toolbox. As the level of vehicle automation increases, it is important to secure V2X communications, ensuring reliable and secure communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and other road users. This study addresses three main topics: the basic components of V2X, the basic components of V2X security, and the practical demonstration of these security components within an application, with a focus on integrating Public Key Infrastructures (PKIs) for secure data exchange. With the upgrade of Unex's V2Xcast[®] Software Development Kit (SDK), integrated into the Routing Core of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox, from version 1.7 to 1.13, the secure transmission of additional message types is supported, and PKI integration is enabled, enhancing the security of V2X communications. The results demonstrate the system's effectiveness in securing communications between Onboard Units (OBUs) and Roadside Units (RSUs), despite certain limitations, such as the inability to send secure Collective Perception Messages (CPMs). This work contributes to developing secure V2X infrastructures, providing insights into the theoretical and practical aspects of V2X security.

Zusammenfassung

Diese Arbeit befasst sich mit der Integration und Demonstration von Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) Sicherheitskomponenten innerhalb der Vehicle Communication Platform to Anything (vehicleCAPTAIN)-Toolbox. Da der Grad der Fahrzeugautomatisierung zunimmt, ist es wichtig, die V2X-Kommunikation abzusichern, um eine zuverlässige und sichere Kommunikation zwischen Fahrzeugen, Infrastruktur und anderen Verkehrsteilnehmern zu gewährleisten. Diese Arbeit konzentriert sich auf drei zentrale Themen: die grundlegenden Komponenten von V2X, die grundlegenden Komponenten der V2X-Sicherheit und die praktische Umsetzung dieser Sicherheitskomponenten in einer Anwendung. Dabei liegt der Fokus besonders auf der Integration von Public Key Infrastructures (PKIs) für einen sicheren Datenaustausch. Mit dem Upgrade des Unex V2Xcast[®] Software Development Kit (SDK), das in den Routing Core der vehicleCAPTAIN-Toolbox integriert ist, von Version 1.7 auf 1.13 wird das sichere Senden zusätzlicher Nachrichtentypen unterstützt und die PKI-Integration ermöglicht, was die Sicherheit der V2X-Kommunikation verbessert. Die Ergebnisse zeigen die Wirksamkeit des Systems bei der Sicherung der Kommunikation zwischen Onboard Units (OBUs) und Roadside Units (RSUs), trotz einiger Einschränkungen, wie zum Beispiel der aktuellen Herausforderung, sichere Collective Perception Messages (CPMs) zu senden. Diese Arbeit trägt zur Entwicklung sicherer V2X-Infrastrukturen bei und gibt Einblicke in die theoretischen und praktischen Aspekte der V2X-Sicherheit.

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1 Introduction

In automated driving, several actors, such as infrastructure, vehicles, and pedestrians, are interconnected. They allow human drivers to let a computer-based system take control of some or all driving tasks, as expressed by Tengilimoglu et al. [1]. Recent innovations in automated driving technologies have increased the development of automated vehicles.

As defined by the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) (J3016) [2], there are six levels of automation, with the highest level defining full vehicle automation. As vehicles reach a higher level of automation, an Intelligent Transport System (ITS) is viable. This infrastructure, enabled by wireless communication between vehicles, other road users, and the surrounding environment, is generally known as V2X (Vehicle-to-Everything) communication. V2X connects communication technologies within ITS, turning it into a Cooperative ITS (C-ITS), as shown in Figure 1.1.

Fig. 1.1: Example of C-ITS [3].

Therefore, securing V2X communication platforms is important to protect them against potential cyber threats.

In V2X security, most approaches focus on ensuring the data is reliable rather than keeping it confidential. Data is signed instead of encrypted, so everyone can access it while trusting the

information. Factors like low delay and low bandwidth are essential to ensure V2X systems work effectively when reliably exchanging information. Hence encryption is omitted.

This work first provides an overview of the basic components of V2X communication and security. This work also shows practical strategies and methods to demonstrate and implement security measures in V2X applications.

The aim of this thesis is set by the three research questions in Chapter 2. These questions will be addressed by describing the technology and definitions behind V2X communication, including its different communication modes in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 continues with the ETSI specification in the European Union (EU) and outlines the security risks within the V2X technology and strategies to secure V2X communication. Chapter 5 shows the hardware preparation for collecting the secured data and the software developed during this work. Chapter 6 analyzes the measurement data collected in the previous chapter and gives answers to the research questions defined earlier. Finally, Chapter 7 concludes this thesis with a conclusion and an outlook for future work.

2 Problem Formulation and Methodology

In recent years, there has been an increasing research interest in V2X technology. However, integration of V2X into the physical world can only be done if we can trust the data which is collected by the interconnected V2X components. To ensure that the data is valid, security measures must be implemented.

This thesis addresses these concerns with the aid of the following three research questions (RQs):

RQ1 What are the basic components of V2X?

As vehicles move closer to full automation, V2X communication is becoming essential for the interaction between vehicles, infrastructure, and other road users. This RQ aims to provide an overview of the basic components of V2X communication. Results should provide insight into how these components function together and what is important for V2X communication.

RQ2 What are the basic components of V2X Security?

As V2X becomes more of a focus in research, the question of how to best secure V2X communications becomes more relevant. This is especially important as systems continue to become more interconnected. This RQ aims to provide an overview of the basic components of V2X security. Results should provide insight into the fundamental security elements and strategies to ensure secure V2X communication.

RQ3 How can the security components be demonstrated in a V2X application?

With a basic understanding of V2X communication and security, we can now look at real-world applications. This RQ examines how security components can be demonstrated in a V2X application. Results should provide insight into practical implementations and which setups are required to demonstrate V2X security measures.

The methodology used in this work for addressing the three RQs is divided into four parts: (i) literature review, (ii) component analysis, (iii) security strategy analysis, and (iv) practical implementation. First, a literature review of the existing V2X communication and security and its standards and protocols is conducted. This provides the basic knowledge to understand V2X systems and their security challenges. Secondly, the basic components of V2X communication and security are identified. Then, these components are analyzed in terms of their role in the V2X infrastructure, how they interact, and where the security risks are. In the third phase, security strategies in V2X infrastructures are examined. Several security measures are considered to provide possible security solutions. Lastly, a practical implementation and testing phase is carried out using the Vehicle Communication Platform to Anything (vehicleCAPTAIN) toolbox. This involves setting up a secure V2X environment and applying security strategies. The setup is then tested in a real-world simulation.

3 Technology and Definitions

This chapter introduces the fundamental technologies and concepts for understanding V2X communication systems. The subchapters explore the basics of V2X communications and how an information exchange is established. Furthermore, it covers Unex's [4] software framework and its components and provides an overview of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] and its Routing Platform, which uses software and hardware from Unex [4].

3.1 Fundamentals of V2X Communication

In automated driving, several components, such as infrastructure, vehicles, and pedestrians, are interconnected, and therefore, an intelligent infrastructure is needed to enable communication between the different elements and provide a C-ITS, as introduced in Chapter 1. The concept of V2X communication refers to the wireless communication concept within C-ITS. V2X enables the exchange of information between vehicles and other road users, as well as with the infrastructure [6, 7].

According to the Federal Ministry for Transport, Innovation, and Technology [7], there are standards from the International Standardisation Organisation (ISO) and the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), which include definitions for C-ITS, with a focus on ITS stations (ITS-Ss). ITS-Ss are the hardware and software units inside a vehicle or installed as a roadside unit. In Europe, C-ITS was introduced based on CEN/ISO TS 19091 [8], which specifies the connection between road safety-relevant cooperative services and radio frequencies. The 5.9 Gigahertz (GHz) band is, in part, designated for C-ITS services in Europe, called ITS in the 5.0 GHz band (ITSG5). C-ITS aims to increase road safety, which can be achieved by sending drivers warnings about traffic disruptions. Traffic disruptions are sent from the ITS-Ss, which can immediately warn drivers about dangerous situations.

Furthermore, a basic C-ITS system may include the following components: (i) the Onboard Unit (OBU), (ii) the Roadside Sensing Unit (RSU), and (iii) the Central/Cloud server [9].

In the context of C-ITS, each ITS-S can communicate with other ITS-Ss. The OBU is the communication component of a mobile ITS-S, often installed in vehicles, as shown in Figure 3.1. It is responsible for the communication between the vehicle and other ITS-Ss on the road, such as roadside infrastructure or other nearby vehicles. On the other hand, the RSU acts as the communication component of a static ITS-S, which is part of the infrastructure. An RSU is positioned along the road and communicates with OBUs in the vehicles while aware of the local topology. Moreover, an RSU provides information about traffic conditions, road hazards, etc., while the ITS Central Station, like a central/cloud server, manages and controls the information collected within the system [10].

Fig. 3.1: Simplified view of ITS environment, following ETSI [11].

The following subchapters will look closer into the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) ITS architecture for the intelligent infrastructure with its layers and the different messages sent during different activities to establish a V2X communication exchange.

3.1.1 V2X Communication Modes

As introduced earlier in this chapter, a V2X technology provides wireless communication between the V2X infrastructure components. A few communication modes, each for a different purpose, can be found in the V2X communication system [12].

The direct communication between the OBUs of two vehicles is called Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V). If a vehicle's OBU communicates with an RSU or relevant application servers, this is called Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I). Moreover, the communication between a vehicle's OBU and one or multiple pedestrians is called Vehicle-to-Person/Pedestrian (V2P). The communication between a base station (BS) and a vehicle's OBU is called Vehicle-to-Network (V2N). Lastly, there is a communication mode called Infrastructure-to-Network (I2N), where communication between infrastructure and network components is established [13].

Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), such as cyclists and pedestrians, are defined as “non-motorized road users” and are also included in the V2X domain [14].

Table 3.1 and Figure 3.2 show the communication modes mentioned. The figure also shows the communication modes for both short-range and long-range communication. Short-range

communication is a type of wireless radio technology, like Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi), used daily for communication between devices, as described by Foubert et al. [15]. In contrast, they describe long-range communication as a method that lets devices talk to each other over long distances without using much energy. The downside is that they send data slowly. An example of long-range communication is the Low-Pan Wide-Area Networks (LPWAN).

Tab. 3.1: Overview about V2X communication types [13, 16].

Communication Type	Description
Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V)	Vehicle communicates directly with another vehicle via their OBUs.
Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I)	Vehicle's OBUs communicate with RSUs.
Vehicle-to-Person/Pedestrian (V2P)	Vehicle's OBU communicates with one or multiple pedestrians through their mobile phone.
Vehicle-to-Network (V2N)	Vehicle's OBUs communicate with external networks through base stations (BS).
Infrastructure-to-Network (I2N)	Infrastructure and network components establish communication through a mobile network.

Fig. 3.2: General overview of a V2X communication, as shown in Yoshizawa et al. [16].

Through V2X communication, it is possible to send standardized messages and exchange them with other nodes in the network. V2X messages are diverse and can include information about nearby components, such as: (i) accidents, provided by Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENMs), (ii) the vehicle's position, speed, and orientation, provided by Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs), and (iii) speed limits and lane statuses, provided by Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Messages (IVIMs) [17, 18].

A more detailed explanation of the V2X message types is described in Chapter 3.1.4.

3.1.2 OSI Reference Model

Conventions and tasks need to be defined for network systems to communicate with each other. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) developed a framework to help create interoperable network systems. This framework is named the Open System Interconnection (OSI) reference model. The OSI reference model is structured in seven vertical layers. Every layer builds on the one below and performs related functions, which improve the services provided. At every level (N), two components, known as layer N peers, exchange Protocol Data Units (PDUs) through a layer-N protocol. The payload of a PDU is called a Service Data Unit (SDU), which is not changed during the transmission from one layer to the next lower layer. The receiving layer then encapsulates the SDU into a new PDU. Layer N-1 adds a header or a footer to the SDU, and after this process, the PDU of layer N becomes the SDU of layer N-1. The seven layers involved in this process are (i) Physical Layer, (ii) Data Link Layer, (iii) Network Layer, (iv) Transport Layer, (v) Session Layer, (vi) Presentation Layer, and (vii) Application Layer [19].

The following sections give an overview of the basic functionalities of each layer of the OSI reference model. This reference model and its layers are the basis for the architecture discussed later in Chapter 3.1.3.

Physical Layer: The Physical Layer defines the physical transmission medium to which a device is connected, e.g., copper and fiber optical cable. Additionally, cable type, signal timing, hubs, network adapters, etc., are elements that are specified in this layer. This layer must define a protocol to establish and terminate connections between two directly connected nodes via a communication medium. The Physical Layer provides a raw and unreliable bit transmission service, which is the basis for the Data Link Layer [19].

Data Link Layer: The Data Link Layer builds on the Physical Layer and defines the format of the data and the method by which it is transferred. In contrast to the Physical Layer, the Data Link Layer provides a reliable data transmission of PDUs, called frames, over a single connection between two systems [19].

The Data Link Layer consists of the Logical Link Control (LLC) and the Medium Access Control (MAC). The Data Link Layer provides framing, flow, and error control functionalities. Furthermore, physical addressing occurs, where a header is added to the frame to define the sender or receiver locally. The LLC and the MAC both take over parts of the framing tasks. Framing is the division of the stream of bits received from the Network Layer into frames. The LLC also handles flow and error control. Flow control is a mechanism used to ensure that data is transmitted at a reasonable rate to prevent overwhelming the receiver. The Data Link Layer applies the error control mechanism to detect and retransmit damaged or lost frames. Meanwhile, the MAC uses access control to decide which device has control over a link if two or more devices are connected to it [20].

Network Layer: The Network Layer builds on the Data Link Layer, organizes the variable length data sequences, called datagrams, to be transferred, and handles reassembly through path determination and logical addressing [19].

The Network Layer layer delivers, forwards, and routes IP (Internet Protocol) packets. Delivery is how a packet is handled by the underlying networks under the control of the Network Layer while forwarding is the way a packet is delivered to the next station.

Routing tables are created to help with the forwarding process. In this layer, routing protocols are used to update the existing routing tables. Additionally, in the Network Layer, logic addressing differentiates the source and destination systems if the packet passes the network boundary [20].

Transport Layer: The Transport Layer is responsible for end-to-end delivery, ensuring the message is valid and arrives in order. To ensure these functionalities are met, error and flow control are used. In contrast to the flow control in the Data Link Layer, the Transport Layer performs this functionality end-to-end rather than across a single connection. Furthermore, error control is performed process-to-process rather than across a single connection. In this layer, a message is divided into segments containing a sequence number so the message can be reassembled correctly at the destination. A Transport Layer protocol can be either connectionless, like the User Datagram Protocol (UDP), or connection-oriented, like the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). If the Transport Layer is connectionless, each segment is treated as a separate packet and delivered to the destination independently. If the Transport Layer is connection-oriented, the packet is delivered only after establishing the connection. Finally, if the data are all transferred, the connection is terminated [20].

Session Layer: The Session Layer establishes, maintains, and synchronizes the communication between systems, and the communication between two processes may take place one way at a time (half-duplex) or two ways at a time (full-duplex) [20].

It is possible to insert checkpoints into a data stream via synchronization to make sure that after a crash, only the data after the last checkpoint needs to be repeated [19].

Presentation Layer: The functionalities of the Presentation Layer are translation, compression, and encryption. Translation is the process of two systems exchanging information about the format of character strings, numbers, etc., but before being transmitted, the information must be changed to bit streams. The Presentation Layer is responsible for the interoperability between these encoding techniques. Compression of data decreases the number of bits in the information. Lastly, encryption ensures privacy by transforming the original information to another form and then sending it [20].

Application Layer: In general, the Application Layer enables the user access to the network and provides user interfaces and support for different services. Application Layer services include a network virtual terminal, a software version of a physical terminal, file transfer, access, and management, mail services, and directory services [20].

Figure 3.3 shows the key functionalities of each layer of the OSI reference model described earlier, with a PDU assigned to each layer.

Fig. 3.3: Overview of the OSI reference model layers and its main functionalities (modified) [21].

3.1.3 ETSI ITS Architecture

ETSI introduced an architecture for C-ITS communications based on the OSI reference model, described in Chapter 3.1.2. According to Nowdehi et al. [22], specific extensions were added to comply with the C-ITS requirements.

This adopted architecture is called ETSI ITS architecture and is the European standard for V2X communication, as defined by ETSI [23]. The ETSI ITS architecture consists of four processing layers: (i) Access Layer, (ii) Networking & Transport Layer, (iii) Facilities Layer, and (iv) Application Layer. The horizontal layers of the ETSI ITS architecture are bordered on each side by two layers: the Management Layer and the Security Layer. Those two layers are horizontally aligned with the other layers, as shown in Figure 3.4.

Fig. 3.4: ETSI ITS-S Reference Architecture, as shown in Spijker et al. [24].

To represent the OSI reference model, the ETSI ITS architecture needs to map the OSI protocol layers to the ITS-S architecture [23].

Specified in [25], the architecture of communications in ITS is called Intelligent Transport System Communications (ITSC). ITSC represents communication protocols, related management, and other functionality. Furthermore, the Access Layer represents the ITSC's OSI layers 1 and 2, the Networking & Transport layer represents the ITSC's OSI layers 3 and 4, and the Facilities Layer represents the ITSC's OSI layers 5, 6, and 7, as shown in Figure 3.5. The ITS Applications

Layer connects to one or more ITS-S applications using the ITS-S services.

The result after the mapping is the ITS communication architecture, where the layer communicates on a peer-to-peer basis [23].

Fig. 3.5: ITSC architecture and its corresponding OSI model layers, as shown in Nowdehi et al. [22].

The following sections give an overview of the basic functionalities of each layer in the ETSI ITS architecture.

Access Layer: The Access Layer consists of the Physical Layer and the Data Link Layer, in which the Physical Layer describes the relationship between a device and a communication medium [25].

The Physical Layer of ITSG5 uses Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) in a “half-clocked” operation across 10 Megahertz (MHz) channels, and the required transfer rates are 3 Megabits per Second (Mbps), 6 Mbps, and 12 Mbps. The Data Link Layer is subdivided into the MAC and the LLC, as mentioned in Chapter 3.1.2. The LLC differentiates between the Network Layer protocols, and the MAC Layer manages the transmissions between ITS-Ss. The Decentralized Congestion Control (DCC) is a management system that regulates the network load by adjusting the number of transmission opportunities an ITS-S has [26].

Network & Transport Layer: ITS network protocols enable the routing of data from source nodes to destination nodes [27].

In the ETSI ITS architecture, as specified in [25], the Network & Transport Layer contains functionalities found in the Network and Transport Layer of the OSI model. This layer includes networking protocols, transport protocols, and management functions for both layers. This design provides flexibility to adapt to the specific needs of the ITSC. Examples of networking protocols include the GeoNetworking (GN) protocol, Internet Protocol Version 6 (IPv6) networking with mobility support, and IPv6 over GN. Standard transport protocols are UDP/TCP, see Chapter 3.1.2, and dedicated ITS transport protocols.

The GN protocol in ITS networks is responsible for transporting data packets and pro-

viding services to the upper layers, such as the ITS transport protocol. The GN protocol uses the ITS Access Layer services to transport the packets. Routers implementing this protocol are called GeoAdhoc routers, each requiring a unique networking address. Furthermore, each GeoAdhoc router should use packet buffers to temporarily store packets within the router while they are being forwarded [28].

One example of the ITS transport protocol is the Basic Transport Protocol (BTP). This lightweight protocol provides unreliable packet transport, meaning the packets can arrive out-of-order or not at all. BTP's primary function is to multiplex messages from different processes at the ITS Facilities Layer, enabling the transmission of packets via the GN protocol. Moreover, it provides the de-multiplexing at the receiving end [29].

Facilities Layer: The Facilities Layer combines functionalities of the OSI Application Layer, the OSI Presentation Layer, and the OSI Session Layer, including functionalities like Abstract Syntax Notation One (ASN.1) encoding/decoding, encryption, and inter-host communication [25].

The Facilities Layer acts as middleware and consists of various facilities, each of which delivers services to ITS applications. Examples of services implemented in this layer are the Cooperative Awareness (CA) basic service and the Decentralized Environment Notification (DEN) basic service. The CA basic service is responsible for managing and distributing CAMs, while the DEN basic service is responsible for the management and distribution of DENMs [11].

Application Layer: The Application Layer delivers ITS services and applications. An ITS application uses the underlying facilities and communication capacities which are provided by the ITS-S. Those services are categorized into three classes: (i) road safety, (ii) traffic efficiency, and (iii) other applications. Applications that can be deployed with reasonable effort within three years after the system's full standardization are called the Basic Set of Applications (BSA) [11].

Management Layer: Congestion control is one of many functionalities in the Management Layer and is called "General Congestion Control" in this layer. Their modifications affect all communication layers and applications. Communication between the different management entity instances of the same ITS-S is done by applying inter-management communication. Moreover, the ITS application management functionality manages the installation and configuration of the ITS-S application. A few more responsibilities of the Management Layer are cross-interface management, inter-unit management communication (IUMC), networking management, station management, management of general, and many more [25].

Security Layer: The Security Layer is responsible for security services, like certificate management, authentication, and authorization, which are provided to the other layers [22]. My thesis focuses on using the provided security functionalities to secure transmitted messages. A more detailed description of this layer can be found in Chapter 4.1.

3.1.4 ETSI V2X Standard Messages

Automated vehicles depend on information. As discussed in Chapter 3.1, this information can be gathered via the wireless connectivity of V2X communication. V2X communication uses services to exchange this information, and the Facility Layer defines the messages for this exchange.

Each V2X service has a Provider Service Identifier (PSID) or ITS-AID (ITS-Application Identifier) of the V2X application, which is the V2X service identifier [30].

As mentioned in Chapter 3.1.1, in V2X are different message types. Important message types with their service types and the PSIDs of each service type are shown in Table 3.2, and the following sections describe them. Table 3.3 shows examples of use cases of V2X messages.

Tab. 3.2: ETSI ITS Message Types and their Service Types [7, 11, 31, 32, 33].

ETSI ITS Message	Service Type	PSID
CAM: Cooperative Awareness Message	CA: Cooperative Awareness	36
DENM: Decentralized Environmental Notification Message	DEN: Decentralized Environmental Notification	37
SPATEM: Signal Phase and Timing Extended Message	TLM: Traffic Light Maneuver	137
MAPEM: MAP (topology) Extended Message	RLT: Road and Lane Topology	138
IVIM: Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message	IVI: Infrastructure to Vehicle Information	139
SREM: Signal Request Extended Message	TLC: Traffic Light Control Request	140
SSEM: Signal request Status Extended Message	TLC: Traffic Light Control	140
CPM: Collective Perception Message	CP: Collective Perception	639

Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM): The Cooperative Awareness (CA) basic service uses CAMs for the exchange of information about the position, presence, dynamics, and basic attributes of its sending party, as described by TransAID (Transition Areas for Infrastructure-Assisted Driving) [31]. The exchange of these messages occurs between the ITS-Ss. The purpose of the exchange is to ensure that the ITS-Ss are aware of each other and to improve cooperative performance.

Example use cases for exchanging CAMs are probing vehicle data and/or event information detected at the roadside and sending information related to traffic management [11].

Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENM): The Decentralized Environmental Notification (DEN) basic service uses DENMs for the exchange of information related to an event that has a potential impact on road safety or traffic conditions. An event is characterized by an event type, an event position, a detection time, and a time duration. Example use cases for exchanging DENMs are collision detection and emergency vehicle approaching [34].

Collective Perception Message (CPM): The Collective Perception (CP) service uses CPMs for the exchange of information about basic information about the transmitting ITS-S, its sensory capabilities, perceived objects, and road-related perception regions to increase awareness of the environment. Moreover, CPMs also provide information about non-V2X-equipped road users and other collision-relevant objects. CPMs are generated during periodic CPM generation events. One example use case for exchanging CPMs is monitoring the status of a detected road user or object and then estimating the collision risk [35].

MAP (topology) Extended Message (MAPEM): The Road and Lane Topology (RLT) service uses MAP (topology) Extended Messages (MAPEMs) for the exchange of infor-

mation about the topology/geometry of a set of lanes. MAPEMs define the topology of lanes or parts of the topology of lanes identified by the intersection reference identifier. This message does not change often. One example use case for exchanging MAPEMs is for defining all the road topological details [32].

Signal Phase and Timing Extended Message (SPATEM): The Traffic Light Maneuver (TLM) service uses Signal Phase and Timing Extended Messages (SPATEMs) to exchange safety-related information to support traffic participants, like vehicles and pedestrians, in executing safe maneuvers in an intersection area. The TLM service informs about the operational states of the traffic light controller, the current signal state, the residual time of the state before changing to the next state, and the allowed maneuvers and provides assistance for crossing. Example use cases for exchanging SPATEMs are the foreseeing of the status for public transport prioritization and giving information about all maneuvers in the area of an intersection [32].

Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message (IVIM): The Infrastructure to Vehicle Information (IVI) service uses IVIMs for the exchange of information on physical road signs, such as static or variable road signs, virtual signs, or road works. Example use cases for exchanging IVIMs are the identification of the service provider for which the roadside ITS-S is allowed to send out IVIMs and to inform the vehicle about the relevant traffic sign information [32].

Signal Request Extended Message (SREM): The Traffic Light Control (TLC) request service uses Signal Request Extended Messages (SREMs) to exchange information sent by ITS-Ss to the traffic infrastructure environment. One example use case for exchanging SREMs is when an SREM is sent in a signalized environment to request priority at a traffic light, allowing the signal to change in favor of the requesting vehicle [32].

Signal request Status Extended Message (SSEM): The Traffic Light Control Request (TLC) status service uses Signal request Status Extended Messages (SSEMs) for the exchange of information sent by the infrastructure to acknowledge the request made by an SREM. An SSEM contains information about whether the request has been granted, canceled, or changed in priority due to a more important signal request, like an ambulance. An example use case for exchanging SSEMs is a reply for granting a bus requesting traffic light signal priority for a defined bus route [32].

Tab. 3.3: Example use cases of V2X messages [7, 11, 31].

Use Case	ETSI ITS Message
Traffic jam ahead warning	DENM
Road works warning	DENM
Weather conditions	DENM
Emergency vehicle approaching	DENM
In-vehicle speed limits	IVIM
Prioritize public transport at traffic signals	SPATEM
Probe vehicle data: CAM aggregation	CAM
Estimating collision risk of object	CPM

3.2 Unex Software Framework

Unex [4] is a company based in Taiwan specializing in V2X software and hardware solutions. With their technology, they are improving how automated vehicles and their systems adapt. Unex works with partners worldwide who use their technology for several V2X projects. Unex offers V2X functional modules called System-on-Modules (SOMs), independent OBUs for vehicles, and RSUs for the infrastructure. Additionally, Unex provides a V2X software called V2Xcast[®]. Unex's SOM hardware is a complete V2X function sub-system with an embedded V2Xcast[®], including the V2X stack and a user-friendly Software Development Kit (SDK), as described by Unex [4]. Unex's OBU and RSU hardware are V2X devices with a globally compatible V2X solution.

According to Unex [4], its V2X stack works with different regional standards, which offers adaptability for other technology needs. The V2Xcast[®] can easily be embedded into any existing vehicle or communication platform. Users can develop further software to enable V2X for their vehicles, intelligent transportation, and smart road traffic applications. The V2Xcast[®] Application Programming Interface (API) keeps all the software benefits, even when the technology or the protocols change. Users can configure the profiles of different V2X messages, see Chapter 3.1.4, for their different needs and develop V2X applications independently. The current version 1.13 of the Unex V2Xcast[®] SDK supports secured V2X communication, supporting the Security Credential Management System (SCMS) and the Credential Management System (CCMS). SCMS is a security system for the United States of America (USA). In contrast, CCMS is an EU C-ITS security system, including the V2X Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) certificate management and private key operations, which will be discussed in Chapter 5.

Fig. 3.6: V2Xcast[®] Functionality in V2X Communication, as shown by Unex [36].

Figure 3.6 shows the Unex's V2Xcast[®] system. At the top are multiple applications that can utilize the V2Xcast[®] SDK. This SDK provides interfaces for communication and supports specific standards. Applications interact with the V2Xcast[®] Services through the transmission (TX) and reception (RX) of V2X messages by the ITS-S. The V2Xcast[®] SDK supports different protocols and standards, like ETSI BTP & GN, see Chapter 3.1.3, IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) & ETSI Security, SCMS & CCMS Protocols and POTI (Position

and Time management). As mentioned earlier in this chapter, users can configure profiles to customize the V2Xcast[®] Service for specific requirements or regional standards, which can be seen in the figure on the right side of the V2Xcast[®] Service.

3.3 Architecture of the Existing Routing Platform

This chapter introduces the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5], designed by Pilz et al. [37], focusing on its Routing Core, used in Chapter 5 for testing purposes. Several components of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] use the software and hardware from Unex, see Chapter 3.2. The following subchapters will introduce the main components of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] and describe how the Routing Platform is structured.

3.3.1 vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox

The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] is a V2X toolbox created by Pilz et al. [37]. The fundamental components of the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit include a hardware setup and a software-based Routing Core. The hardware setup, which currently supports ITSG5 communication via the Unex SOM301-E and Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) via Ethernet or plugged-in mobile network connections, is independent of the software. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] consists of four groups: (i) ITS Message Libraries, (ii) Platform, (iii) ROS2 (Robot Operating System 2) Support, and (iv) Tools, which are shown in Figure 3.7. Each group consists of projects on Github [5] that are available as FOSS (Free and Open-Source Software). As described by Pilz et al. [37], they developed a generator script that creates a ready-to-use C and C++ library from the ETSI-provided message exchange protocol for all V2X-related standards, using ASN.1.

This library is relevant for the V2X sending and receiving functions in the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5], also used in the security testing part described in Chapter 5.

Fig. 3.7: Repository structure of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox, as shown in Pilz et al. [37].

3.3.2 Routing Platform

One key component of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] is the Routing Core, a message-passing software. The main components in the High-Level Architecture (HLA) of the vehicleCAPTAIN Routing Core work as follows: (i) Communication technologies like Wi-Fi, 5G, and ITS G5 connect to their corresponding interfaces; (ii) the interfaces connect to the V2X IO (Input/Output) Control, which manages the communication flow with the help of the Rating Handler and the Communication Control; (iii) the V2X Routing Middleware manages the routing of messages and makes sure that the messages are directed to the correct destination through the system; and finally (iv) the data manipulation happens onboard or externally, where the messages are decoded, processed and re-encoded before they are transmitted or received.

In more detail, a ZMQ (Zero Message Queueing) interface is provided by the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit and handles the message sending and receiving as byte streams, as described by Pilz et al. [37]. The sending of messages is passed to the Routing part, but in the simplest case, the messages go directly to the Communication Control. The Communication Control selects the message type or other parameters to decide which interface to distribute the message. The interface implementation then transmits each message via the individual hardware interface. The raw message is kept in the incoming queue until the Communication Control collects it. If collected, the Communication Control forwards the message to the Routing part, as shown in Figure 3.8.

Fig. 3.8: The HLA of the vehicleCAPTAIN Routing Core, as shown in Pilz et al. [37].

4 V2X Security

Over the past decade, research and pilot projects focusing on V2X communication have extended our knowledge of applications in the automated driving domain. These developments will improve overall traffic safety, such as reducing the number of accidents and decreasing travel time. However, an open communication interface, such as V2X, introduces new challenges for cybersecurity [38].

Implementing key security and privacy requirements into the V2X infrastructure is important. To create a secure V2X infrastructure, it is important to be aware of the increasing number of attacks and implement security measures to prevent them [16].

The following subchapters give an overview of the ITS security architecture, the security risks within V2X, strategies to secure V2X communication, and lastly, how security measures are integrated into a V2X infrastructure.

4.1 Security Layer

This work focuses on the ETSI ITS security and privacy solution within the European Union (EU), including its implementation and integration into the V2X infrastructure.

The horizontal layers of the ETSI ITS architecture, see Chapter 3.1.3, are bordered on each side by two layers: (i) the Management Layer and (ii) the Security Layer, as mentioned in Chapter 3.1.3.

The Security Layer can be seen as one component divided into four ITS processing layers: ITS (i) Application, (ii) Facilities, (iii) Networking & Transport, and (iv) Access Layer, as shown in Figure 4.1. Specified in [23], the Security Layer includes two additional parts: Security Management Services and Security Defense Layer. Together, these components provide security services to secure communications between ITS-Ss. The security services operate in the ITS layers or inside the Security Management Layer and are responsible for using and changing identification information inside one ITS-S. The Security Defense Layer protects critical data and increases the chances of detecting an attack.

The Security Management Layer manages the communications to an ITS-S and grants access to the Management Information Base (MIB) [25].

Examples of the general functionality of the Security Layer are firewall and intrusion management, authentication, authorization and profile management, identity, crypto key, and certificate management, a common Security Information Base (SIB), and Hardware Security Modules (HSM) [25].

Fig. 4.1: Layered ITS security architecture, following ETSI [23].

In the Facilities Layer, security services like managing security associations, validating the payload’s sequence number, and ensuring the payload’s plausibility can be found.

In the Network & Transport Layer, security services like verifying a signature, validating the message generation time, or validating message authorization can be found.

In the Access Layer, the identification security service can be found.

In the Security Management Layer, security services like enrolment, authorization, remote management, and identity management can be found.

Figure 4.2 shows the specific security services in each layer mentioned earlier.

Fig. 4.2: Security Services within the ITS-S architecture, following ETSI [23].

4.2 Security Risks within V2X

“Cybersecurity includes all activities and measures intended to prevent and cover any threats regarding information systems connected to the cyberspace.”-Beissel [39]

Cybersecurity has three basic principles: confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA). These principles of cybersecurity are described as the CIA triad and are shown in Figure 4.3. Confidentiality stands for preventing stealing and misusing sensitive information, integrity focuses on preventing manipulation or damage of information, and availability represents preventing attacks on information systems availability [39].

Fig. 4.3: CIA triad, as shown by Beissel [39].

As highlighted by Asaju et al. [12], the interconnection of components and its wireless features are reasons why the V2X infrastructure is vulnerable to various security threats. Maintaining privacy inside a V2X communication is challenging but essential to ensure user privacy. These communications can contain sensitive information about the location, vehicle status, or driving behavior.

For V2X security requirements, extended principles can be defined, which are authenticity and non-repudiation [9]. Authenticity not only refers to being an authentic and validatable entity but can also be extended to the authenticity and validity of data, while non-repudiation prevents a party, sender or receiver, from contesting an action being made [39]. This includes logging and auditing the user’s actions to assign each act to a specific party [40]. All five principles united represent the concepts of confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity, and non-repudiation (CIAAN) [41], as shown in Figure 4.4.

Fig. 4.4: CIAAN.

In addition, attacks in a V2X infrastructure can be categorized as active or passive. An active attack is described as an active interaction with the system, while during a passive attack, the attacker is passively monitoring the system and is eavesdropping on sensitive information like certificates or private keys [42].

Tables 4.1 and 4.2 show an overview of the key security threats of V2X infrastructures and a brief description of each threat. Each threat is assigned to one of the previously mentioned principles of CIAAN.

Tab. 4.1: Key security threats and their CIAAN principles (Part 1) [9, 12].

Threat Type	CIAAN Principle	Description
Alter or inject false messages attack	Integrity	An attacker intercepts and potentially alters the communication between two parties, leading to data manipulation, denial of service, or unauthorized access. Example: Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) attack.
Spoofing and Impersonation	Integrity, Authenticity	An attacker impersonates other vehicles or infrastructure components to insert manipulated information, creating misleading and potentially dangerous situations.
Denial of Service (DoS)	Availability	An attacker overwhelms the network with excessive traffic or disrupts communication, leading to degraded service or complete unavailability.
Eavesdropping attack	Confidentiality	An attacker passively listens to private communications within the V2X network to gather sensitive information.
Blackhole and Greyhole attacks	Availability	The infiltrated node stops replaying packets to nodes next to them and consequently obstructs the communication over the whole network. The attacker drops all the packets that are received during a blackhole attack. The difference from a greyhole attack is that the attacker drops some packets.
Coalition and platooning attacks	Availability	Infiltrated nodes work together to carry out malicious actions. Examples are blocking information and isolating authorized vehicles.
Replay attack	Integrity	An attacker infiltrates a node and then captures the packets. The captured packets are replayed at different times to act like they were originally sent by the genuine sender.

Tab. 4.2: Key security threats and their CIAAN principles (Part 2) [9, 12].

Threat Type	CIAAN Principle	Description
Location tracking	Confidentiality	An attacker collects shared location information from vehicular applications and uses them to track users.
Certificate replication attack	Authenticity	An attacker uses replicated certificates and digital signatures to confuse authorities and prevent them from discovering their intent.
Sybil attack	Authenticity	One node pretends to be many fake identities.
Any	Non-Repudiation	If one node trusts another, it will continue communicating with it, even if it has a fake identity. This scenario violates some characteristics of non-repudiation.

For better understanding and illustration, the following Figure 4.5 shows three security attacks: (i) a DoS attack, (ii) a Sybil attack, and (ii) an Inject false message attack, described in the Tables 4.1 and 4.2 above. These three attacks are possible within the existing V2X communication systems.

Fig. 4.5: High-Level illustration of three attacks in the V2X infrastructure with malicious (black) and victim (blue) vehicles: (a) DoS attacks: 1. attacker floods message packets and 2. overwhelms the network; (b) Sybil attacks: attacker pretends to be two fake identities and sends false messages; (c) Inject false message attacks: the attacker intercepts and sends altered fake information, as shown in Hasan et al. [42].

4.3 Strategies for Secure V2X Communication

As vehicles become more interconnected with each other and their surrounding infrastructure, and as V2X applications rely on information exchange within the V2X environment, the risk of cyber threats increases. This chapter discusses the security solutions to meet the security requirements in V2X communication.

As discussed by Sedar et al. [38], security solutions can be classified into two categories: (i) proactive and (ii) reactive defense mechanisms. Proactive security approaches can be used to identify V2X security weaknesses and act before they occur. In contrast, responding to V2X security attacks after they occur is a reactive security approach. Proactive security approaches,

like PKI, digital signatures or certificates, or proprietary protocols, ensure security by using security policies, such as checking authenticity and integrity with digital signatures and controlling access to services through authorization.

The following sections give an overview of different security methods in proactive and reactive security approaches.

Proactive Security

Proactive security mechanisms, as introduced earlier in this chapter, can be divided into three classes: (i) cryptography-based, (ii) physical layer security, and (iii) privacy preservation [38], as shown in Figure 4.6.

The first classification of proactive security solutions is the cryptography-based security approach. This approach ensures authenticity, availability, confidentiality, and integrity security requirements. The cryptography-based security approach can be divided into four categories: (i) PKI-based asymmetric, (ii) symmetric, (iii) identity-based, and (iv) attribute-based [38].

PKI-based asymmetric cryptography provides security by acting as a Trusted Third Party (TTP). It manages public keys and connects users, which ensures C-ITS security [38].

Symmetric cryptography provides data encryption and message integrity checks. In contrast to the asymmetric approach, symmetric schemes do not depend on the underlying infrastructure. However, they are less secure because the entire system is compromised if the secret key is exposed since both parties use the same shared key for communicating [38].

Identity-based cryptography (IBC) is asymmetric cryptography that uses device or user identities, rather than digital certificates, to link public keys. This approach is less secure than the PKI-based asymmetric method but simplifies the key management process [38].

Attribute-based encryption (ABE) is an extended concept of IBC. In this approach, public keys are defined based on attributes. In ABE, a user's keys and ciphertexts are tagged with descriptive attributes. A specific key can decrypt a ciphertext only if the attributes of the ciphertext match those of the user's key [38].

The second classification of proactive security solutions is Physical Layer Security (PLS). PLS uses the diffusion and superposition of transmitted signals to provide data confidentiality. It uses mechanisms that reduce the chance of potential eavesdroppers gathering information. Furthermore, PLS approaches are identified as non-cryptographic security solutions [38].

The third classification of proactive security solutions is privacy preservation. Privacy preservation involves protecting both the identity and location information of vehicles. To ensure privacy, properties such as untraceability and unlinkability must be satisfied by privacy solutions. Untraceability means that a vehicle's actions should not be traceable, while unlinkability ensures that unauthorized persons cannot link a vehicle's identity to its driver [38].

Reactive Security

Proactive security mechanisms, as introduced earlier in this chapter, can be divided into three classes: (i) signature-based, (ii) anomaly-based, and (iii) context-based, as discussed by Sedar et al. [38], and shown in Figure 4.6. All proactive security methods verify whether the received information conforms to system or protocol operation norms.

The first classification of reactive security solutions is the signature-based approach. This approach detects attacks by comparing network traffic to known attack signatures. However, it can only identify previously known attacks [38].

The second classification of reactive security solutions is the anomaly-based approach. This approach compares incoming information with normal system behavior and requires defining normal operational behavior. However, this approach often generates false alarms [38].

The third classification of reactive security solutions is the context-based approach. This approach uses the built-in features of V2X communication and safety applications. Each vehicle collects information from its surroundings and creates an independent view of the current system status and local environment [38].

Figure 4.6 shows that the combination of the anomaly-based and the context-based approach can be further divided into (i) entity-centric and (ii) data-centric detection mechanisms. Entity-centric mechanisms for misbehavior detection can be divided into two categories: i) behavioral and ii) trust-based, and data-centric mechanisms can be divided into two categories as well: (i) plausibility-based and (ii) consistency-based.

Fig. 4.6: Security approaches in V2X communication, as shown in Sedar et al. [38].

4.4 Integration of Security Measures

For this work, the integration of the PKI-based asymmetric security approach, introduced in Chapter 4.3, will be further discussed.

Security services, see Chapter 4.1, require more than one element to communicate within their infrastructure, as described by ETSI [23]. This is shown in Figure 4.7, where an ITS-enabled

vehicle needs to communicate with the following entities: (i) an Enrolment Authority (EA), (ii) an Authorization Authority (AA), (iii) other ITS-equipped vehicles, and (iv) other ITS-equipped devices, like roadside units, and personal units, like portable devices. The EA is responsible for enrolling the vehicle into the ITS network. The AA manages the authorization of the vehicle. This makes sure that the vehicle has permission to communicate in this network. Within this network, ITS-Ss communicate with each other by sending V2X messages, like CAMs and DENMs, see Chapter 3.1.4.

Fig. 4.7: ITS communications example scenario, as shown by ETSI [23].

In more detail, ITS communication relies on trust relationships using certificates issued by TTPs, with the main TTP being the EA. To access the ITS system, an ITS-S must have an enrolment certificate, which gives permission to be part of the ITS and to use other services. Before an ITS-S can use the ITS applications and services, it is required to have cryptographically signed certificates, called Authorization Tickets (ATs), from the AA [23].

As described by ETSI [23], the process to require an AT consists of three phases: (i) initialization, (ii) enrolment, and (ii) authorization. In the initialization phase, a set of credentials is established. These include (i) a canonical unique and immutable identity for the ITS-S, (ii) a canonical public and private cryptographic key pair for the ITS-S, a generic profile of the properties of the ITS-S, and optionally (iv) a cryptography self-signed bootstrap certificate that links the ITS-S' canonical identity with its public key and its generic profile. The enrolment phase uses the canonical credentials to create Enrolment Credentials (ECs) at initialization. These previously issued ECs are used to renew ECs. In the authorization phase, ECs establish a set of authorization credentials. The identity management service, see Chapter 4.1, manages the creation, storage, certification, and revocation of the credentials [23].

Many V2X applications rely on broadcast messages addressing all recipients, as discussed by ETSI [23]. They also define that confidentiality, see Chapter 4.2, is not required except to protect the sender's identity. This can be achieved by ensuring that all messages are sent pseudonymously.

Fig. 4.8: PKI architecture, as shown by ETSI [23].

Figure 4.8 shows the architecture of the C-ITS SCMS, also called the C-ITS Trust Model, a form of a PKI. In this PKI, each element has a specific role. The Root Certification Authority (CA) is the highest level CA and provides EA and AA with proof that they are authorized to issue credentials. Each Root CA stores its certificate and trust list information (CRL, CTL) in a local repository. The Misbehaviour Authority (MA) creates reports based on misbehavior activities. It also investigates potentially misbehaving ITS-Ss and takes appropriate action [23].

Europe's main governance roles are defined in the C-ITS Platform Certificate Policy document [43] and are responsible for the C-ITS trust management. These roles include (i) Policy Authority, (ii) Trust List Manager (TLM), and (iii) C-ITS Point of Contact (CPOC). The Policy Authority is the top-level role of the C-ITS trust system. It manages the C-ITS trust system and authorizes the TLM and CPOC to operate within it. It also determines the trustworthiness of Root CAs. The CPOC is a unique entity designated by the Policy Authority. It establishes and contributes to ensuring the communication exchange between the Root CAs, collects the Root CA certificates, and provides them to the TLM. The TLM creates the list of Root CA certificates and TLM certificates [23].

Through this framework, the PKI supports the secure exchange of V2X messages, such as CAMs, ensuring reliable communication between vehicles, which is essential for maintaining trust in the V2X message exchange.

As specified in [45], secured messages must have a specific structure. This document also defines the specific security profiles for V2X messages, like CAMs and DENMs. Every message includes its own certificate and signature information because this information must be processed quickly due to its delay sensitivity [44].

Fig. 4.9: Structure of a Secured CAM, as shown in Lonc et al. [44].

In ETSI TS 103 097 [45] is specified how a message structure, as shown in Figure 4.9, is encoded and processed by the security services in the ITS-S Security Layer. The secured part of the message structure consists of a protocol version, header fields, a payload field, and trailer fields, with the header and trailer fields having adjustable lengths. Furthermore, the header and trailer fields must start with a length field that specifies the total length of the header or trailer in bytes. The payload field should contain a single message payload. Each field in the header, payload, and trailer must be preceded by a HeaderFieldType, PayloadType, and TrailerFieldType, respectively. The security layer uses information from the header fields, like *generation_time*, *its_ai*, *expiration*, *generation_location*, *signer_info*, and *encryption_parameters*, and can be extended with additional fields. Only one payload field is allowed, which starts with the PayloadType and the payload data length. The trailer field length can be adjusted [44].

The ITS-AID in the ETSI architecture identifies a specific message, service, or application. The ITS-AID field in the ITS-S certificate (AT) shows the permissions given to a vehicle, such as being allowed to send CAMs. The Service Specific Permissions (SSP) field details specific permissions within a message, service, or application. Permissions in an ITS-S's certificate are defined by ITS-AID and SSP pairs, with a single certificate able to contain multiple such pairs [44].

In conclusion, the V2X security framework ensures that messages are securely sent while protecting the sender's identity. It uses a clear structure and defined permissions to enable secure communication within the ITS system.

5 V2X Security within the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox

Security is an important factor regarding the future of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5]. To ensure that no third party is manipulating information, it is important to secure the messages that are sent and received in our projects. The authorization process for the involved sender and receiver makes the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] a reliable part of multiple projects and future innovations. The company Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH [46] has a license to use Unex's [4] software and hardware solutions. This license includes the GN Daemon Security, which will be discussed in Chapter 5.1. It is also possible to include a PKI infrastructure, and therefore, the Qualified Trust Service Provider (QTSP) Microsec [47] grants us access to their innovative PKI security solution, which will be discussed in Chapter 5.2.

5.1 GN Daemon Security

According to Unex [48], see Chapter 3.2, its GN library was created to provide an easy way to use the ETSI GN basic transport protocol services. Figure 5.1 shows the Unex [4] ETSI GN communication system, featuring the Unex [4] GN protocol SDK framework. This protocol includes the GN service program and API library. A local ITS-S can transmit and receive ETSI ITS packets through the application program with its components. It is important to check if one Unex [4] GN service daemon program is running before communicating with any GN APIs.

In more detail, the overall system is contained within a local ITS-S, shown in Figure 5.1. The figure shows the communication flow and data handling between the different components in the V2X communication system provided by Unex [4]. The remote ITS-S represents a remote ITS-S that sends and receives data packets. The central component of the figure is the ETSI ITS radio interface, which is responsible for managing the communication with the remote ITS-S. Moreover, the Unex [4] GN service daemon handles the different services related to packet management and security. Connected to the Unex [4] GN service daemon is the profile mapping table, which handles authentication and data security. The GN daemon configuration file, called *gnd.json*, contains the configuration used by the profile mapping table, which will be discussed later. From the Unex [4] ITS radio interface to the Unex [4] GN service daemon, the decapsulation of incoming RX packets is shown. The encapsulation of outgoing TX packets is handled by the Unex [4] GN service daemon and then sent back to the ETSI ITS radio interface. Applications send protocol requests via Inter-Process Communication (IPC) to the Unex [4] GN service daemon, requesting to encapsulate data for transmission.

Fig. 5.1: Unex [4] ETSI GN Protocol SDK Framework and Security Process Flow.

The following subchapters include the necessary steps to successfully deploy a secure V2X communication with two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits.

5.1.1 Preparation

Initially, we were using the V2Xcast[®] SDK version 1.7 in the Routing Core of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5], but we upgraded to version 1.13 as part of the preparation. While secure CAMs and DENMs could already be transmitted in the earlier version, the upgrade enabled the transmission of additional message types, such as IVIM, MAPEM, SPATEM, SREM, and SSEM.

Important: Both vehicleCAPTAIN development kits, which are used for sending and receiving, need to have the certificates installed on their modules.

First, plug the module into the computer and ensure that the module’s fixed IP address can be reached by manually setting the IP address, netmask, and gateway for the Ethernet connection on the computer.

The following files must be uploaded in the following order:

1. GN Daemon Configuration; fixed filename: “*gnd.json*”
2. Certificate Request Config; fixed filename: “*ieee_sec_ee_request_cfg.json*”
3. Demo certificates provided by Unex [4]
4. V2Xcast Configuration file; no fixed filename: “*{FILENAME}.json*”

When uploading configuration files from a directory on the computer, it is necessary to provide the required library files to ensure that the following commands can be executed properly. To do this, insert the command shown in Source 5.1 in front of all subsequent commands. This command temporarily sets the LD_LIBRARY_PATH to include the lib directory in the current

working directory, ensuring that the system can find and load the necessary dynamic libraries to execute the commands.

```
LD_LIBRARY_PATH=$(pwd)/lib
```

Src. 5.1: Library Path.

Note: If secured transmission of the messages is not needed, the *AID* field in the V2Xcast Configuration file should be set to *-1*, but configuring unsecured and secured messages at the same time is not possible. Moreover, only the GN Daemon configuration file and the V2Xcast configuration file need to be uploaded if unsecured transmission is required.

The following sections provide an overview of the purpose of these files and explain how they should be structured.

GN Daemon Configuration: The `gnd.json` file, shown in Source 5.2, contains the configuration settings for the GN Daemon. At the top of the file, parameters such as *station.protocol*, *station.type*, and *fixed_position.is_enabled* are defined. To enable the security mechanism, the field *security.is_mib_its_gn_security_enabled* must be set to *true*. The *aid_profiles* field includes the profile settings for different V2X message types, represented by their AID or PSID, as shown in Table 3.2. Currently, the security profile of the GN Daemon supports only the `ISC_PROFILE_SIGN`, which is a generic security profile for signed messages [48].

```
{
  ...
  "security": {
    "is_mib_its_gn_security_enabled": true, <----- Enabled
    "is_mib_its_gn_anonymous_addr_enabled": false,
    "is_mib_its_gn_decap_result_strict": false,
    "aid_profile": [
      {
        "aid": 36,
        "profile_name": "ISC_PROFILE_SIGN"
      },
      ...
    ]
  }
}
```

Src. 5.2: Structure of the `gnd.json` file.

The `gnd.json` file needs to be uploaded with the command shown in Source 5.3.

```
./v2xcast_manager -m put -f {PATH_TO_FILE}/gnd.json {
  ↪ IP_ADDRESS_MODULE}/cfg/gnd
```

Src. 5.3: Uploading `gnd.json` to module.

Certificate Request Config: The Certificate Request Config file, as shown in Source 5.4, must be configured before users install or update the demo certificates provided by Unex [4]. This file restricts the types of certificates that can be installed on the module. The

current maximum number of different certificate types is 10. After setting up this file, the device should be rebooted. The *SDEE_NAME* field can be modified by the user. The user can specify the ATs to be uploaded to the module by configuring them in the *AuthorityTickets* field. This field includes the *DESCRIPTION* field, where the message type is specified. The maximum length of *DESCRIPTION* is 16 characters. The *AppPermission* field, which includes the respective *PSID* and *SSP*, see Chapter 4.4, is also part of this configuration. The maximum number of *AppPermissions* for a certificate is 16, and the maximum length of the *SSP* field is 16 bytes. The *CCMS_RequestEnable* field is set to *false* because the certificates have not yet been downloaded from a PKI [48].

```

{
  "EndEntitiesCertRequest": [
    {
      "SDEE_Name": "{SDEE_NAME}",
      "AuthorityTickets": [
        {
          "DESCRIPTION": "CAM",
          "AppPermission": [
            {
              "PSID": 36,
              "SSP": "{SSP}"
            }
          ]
        },
        {
          "DESCRIPTION": "DENM",
          "AppPermission": [
            {
              "PSID": 37,
              "SSP": "{SSP}"
            }
          ]
        },
        ...
      ]
    }
  ],
  "CCMS_RequestEnable": false
}

```

Src. 5.4: Structure of Certificate Request Config file.

The command for uploading the Certificate Request Config file is shown in Source 5.5.

```

./v2xcast_manager -m put -f {PATH_TO_FILE}/ieee_sec_ee_request_cfg.json {
  ↪ IP_ADDRESS_MODULE}/upld/sec_cfg

```

Src. 5.5: Uploading Certificate Request Config file to module.

Demo Certificates: Copy the demo certificates into a folder with easy access.

Important: The configuration file `gnd.json` must include the same message types in its configuration that are intended for certificate uploads. Otherwise, errors will occur, and secure transmission will not be possible.

Before uploading the certificates, it is necessary to create specific folders for them. Instead of the “*test*” folder, a different name can be chosen. The `tree` command will list the directory where the certificates are copied, as shown in Figure 5.2.

The commands for uploading the certificates need to be executed as shown in Source 5.6.

```
mkdir -p test/ee
mkdir -p test/ca
cp {PATH_TO_FILE}/t1m.cert test/ca/
cp {PATH_TO_FILE}/etsi_root.cert test/ca/
cp {PATH_TO_FILE}/etsi_aa.cert test/ca/
cp {PATH_TO_FILE}/etsi_aa.cert test/ca/
cp {PATH_TO_FILE}/etsi_at_* test/ee/
tree test/
```

Src. 5.6: Create folders for certificate upload.

```
test/
├── ca
│   ├── etsi_aa.cert
│   ├── etsi_root.cert
│   └── t1m.cert
└── ee
    ├── etsi_at_cam.cert
    ├── etsi_at_cam.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_denm.cert
    ├── etsi_at_denm.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_gn_mng.cert
    ├── etsi_at_gn_mng.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_ivi.cert
    ├── etsi_at_ivi.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_mapem.cert
    ├── etsi_at_mapem.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_rtcmem.cert
    ├── etsi_at_rtcmem.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_saem.cert
    ├── etsi_at_saem.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_spatem.cert
    ├── etsi_at_spatem.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_srem.cert
    ├── etsi_at_srem.ecdsa.priv
    ├── etsi_at_ssem.cert
    └── etsi_at_ssem.ecdsa.priv

2 directories, 23 files
```

Fig. 5.2: Result of `tree` command.

The demo certificates must be uploaded with the command shown in Source 5.7.

```
./v2xcast_manager -m put -c -sdee {SDEE_NAME} -path test/ {
  ↪ IP_ADDRESS_MODULE}/upld/cert
```

Src. 5.7: Upload Certificates.

Figure 5.3 shows the successful upload of the certificate to the module.

```
=====
material path = test/
sdee name = ETSI_SEC
=====
=> [1]CA cert(tlm.cert)
=> [2]CA cert(etsi_root.cert)
=> [3]CA cert(etsi_aa.cert)
=====
valid num of CA certificate materials (3):
=====
=> [1]EE cert(etsi_at_mapem.cert)
=> [1]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_mapem.ecdsa.priv)
=> [2]EE cert(etsi_at_cam.cert)
=> [2]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_cam.ecdsa.priv)
=> [3]EE cert(etsi_at_denm.cert)
=> [3]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_denm.ecdsa.priv)
=> [4]EE cert(etsi_at_gn_mng.cert)
=> [4]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_gn_mng.ecdsa.priv)
=> [5]EE cert(etsi_at_ssem.cert)
=> [5]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_ssem.ecdsa.priv)
=> [6]EE cert(etsi_at_spatem.cert)
=> [6]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_spatem.ecdsa.priv)
=> [7]EE cert(etsi_at_ivi.cert)
=> [7]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_ivi.ecdsa.priv)
=> [8]EE cert(etsi_at_rtcem.cert)
=> [8]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_rtcem.ecdsa.priv)
=> [9]EE cert(etsi_at_srem.cert)
=> [9]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_srem.ecdsa.priv)
=> [10]EE cert(etsi_at_saem.cert)
=> [10]EE ecdsa privkey(etsi_at_saem.ecdsa.priv)
=====
valid num of EE certificate materials (10):
v2xcastd upload certificates successfully
```

Fig. 5.3: Result of successfully uploading the demo certificates.

V2Xcast Configuration file: The structure of a V2Xcast Configuration file can be seen in Source 5.8. Here, the V2Xcast SDK interacts with Unex [4] devices via casters. A caster logically maps to various profile settings. The POTI profile is always invoked. Each caster profile can include several casters, but each caster must be unique within this file. The value of the *Identifier (ID)* field should be a continuous number starting from zero. The maximum number of casters allowed in this file is eight. In the *AID* field under Security, the AID or PSID, as described previously, should be entered. The *Caster Communication Mode* field specifies the communication mode, such as the V2Xcast API, that we intend to use. The *BTP Type* field determines whether to use connection-oriented or connectionless services. The *Source and Destination Port* fields specify the respective ports. The *TX Power* field allows us to set the transmission power. The *TX Data Rate* field specifies the transmission data rate. The *Transport Type* field sets the GN transport type. The *TX*

Traffic Class ID field categorizes and prioritizes different types of data traffic based on their urgency and importance. The *TX Maximum Packet Lifetime* field can be set from 0 up to 600 seconds, the *TX Repetition Interval* can be set from 0.100 to 65535 milliseconds, and the *TX Maximum Repetition Time* can be set from 0.100 to 65535 milliseconds. The *TX Maximum Hop Limit* sets an upper boundary on the number of hops that a message is allowed to make. The *Target Shape* can be Circular, Rectangular, or Ellipsoidal. Distance A and B can be set from 1 to 65535 meters, and the Angle from 0 to 359 degrees [48].

Important: Only message types for which a certificate is installed on the module can be specified in the caster configuration file and the configuration of secured and unsecured messages at the same time is not possible.

```

{
  "Caster Profile": [
    {
      "ID": 0,
      "Description": "CAM example",
      "Caster Comm. Mode": "{CASTER_COMM_MODE}",
      "BTP":
      {
        "BTP Type": "{BTP_TYPE}",
        "Source Port": {SOURCE_PORT},
        "Destination Port": {DESTINATION_PORT},
        "TX Power": {TX_PORT},
        "TX Data Rate": {TX_DATA_RATE}
      },
      "GN":
      {
        "Transport Type": "{TRANSPORT_TYPE}",
        "TX Traffic Class ID": {TX_TRA_CLASS_ID},
        "TX Maximum Packet Lifetime": {TX_MAX_PACKET_LIFETIME},
        "TX Repetition Interval": {TX_REP_INTERVAL},
        "TX Maximum Repetition Time": {TX_MAX_REP_TIME}
      },
      "Security":
      {
        "AID": 36
      },
      "Channel Profile Name": "{CHANNEL_PROFILE}"
    }, ...
  ],
  "POTI Profile": [
    {
      "Description": "Internal POTI",
      "Type": "Publisher"
    }
  ]
}

```

Src. 5.8: Structure of the V2Xcast Configuration file.

The V2Xcast Configuration file must be uploaded with the command shown in Source 5.9.

```
./v2xcast_manager -m put -f {PATH_TO_FILE}/{FILENAME}.json {
  ↪ IP_ADDRESS_MODULE}/cfg/v2xcast
```

Src. 5.9: Uploading V2Xcast Configuration file to module.

To see all the uploaded certificates on the module, the command in Source 5.10 should be used, and the result should look like in Figure 5.4

```
./v2xcast_manager -m get {IP_ADDRESS_MODULE}/sec_db?{SDEE_NAME}
```

Src. 5.10: Command to get certificate overview on module.

```
===== CA certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8
=====
UNEX AA Certificate   Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████
UNEX Root Certificate Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████
=====

===== HOME PKI certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8
=====
EU-TLM_L0           Fri May 14 21:59:58 2021    Wed May 14 21:16:46 2025    ██████████
=====

===== Canonical Info =====
canonical id        canonical private key status  canonical public key(uncompressed)
=====

===== EE certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8            psid
=====
etsi_at_denm        Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        37
etsi_at_ssem        Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        637
etsi_at_gn_mng      Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        141
etsi_at_vam         Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        638
etsi_at_cam         Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        36
etsi_at_spatem      Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        137
etsi_at_saem        Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        540801
etsi_at_srem        Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        140
etsi_at_mapem       Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        138
etsi_at_ivi         Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        139
etsi_at_rtcmem      Wed Mar 31 16:00:00 2021    Tue Apr  1 02:12:00 2031    ██████████        540802
=====
```

Fig. 5.4: List of all certificates on module.

5.1.2 Measurement Setup

The setup includes two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits positioned beside each other, as shown in Figure 5.5. Using one vehicleCAPTAIN development kit, the RSU is simulated, while the other one simulates the OBU. The Sender Example and the Receiver Example of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] are used to simulate this scenario, both of which are Docker [49] containers. After successfully setting up the test scenario, the sender sends secured CAMs while the receiver receives them. The two projects are available as FOSS, and the respective instructions to deploy them are available on Github [5]. After correctly setting up the test environment, the messages should arrive with integrity at the destination.

Fig. 5.5: Test scenario: two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits beside each other.

5.1.3 Measurements

Figure 5.6 shows the Sender Example and Figure 5.7 shows the Receiver Example from the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5], demonstrating the successful transmission of secured CAMs with the demo certificates. In the figure, the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit on the left sends the secured CAMs, while the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit on the right successfully receives them.

```

neubaueradm@INNBI :~$ docker exec -it cpp_sender-demo ./cppSender [IP_ADDRESS] 5555 2 1
main()
main(): connect ZMQ (tcp://[IP_ADDRESS]:5555)

main(): main loop

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- --- CAM --- --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #0

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- --- CAM --- --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #1

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- --- CAM --- --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #2

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- --- CAM --- --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #3

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- --- CAM --- --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #4

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- --- CAM --- --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #5

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- --- CAM --- --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #6

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- --- CAM --- --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #7

```

Fig. 5.6: Successful sender simulation with demo certificates.

Figure 5.8 shows the secured CAM as described in Chapter 4.4. The secured CAM was captured via Wireshark [50] with a Cohda [51] module. This secured CAM includes digital signatures and security fields to ensure the message’s authenticity and integrity during transmission.

5.2 V2X PKI

The following chapters outline the necessary steps to successfully deploy a secure V2X communication between two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits using a PKI, utilizing the tools provided by Microsec [47].

5.2.1 Preparation

The upgrade of the Routing Core was also essential here, see Chapter 5.1.1, to support the secure transmission of additional message types, and it was particularly important for PKI integration because, with the upgrade, the CCMS client became available, which is needed for managing and downloading PKI certificates.

Note: The Routing Core needs to be slightly modified by not adding *BTP_PORT_GPC* to the BTP Ports in *CommunicationControl* because Microsec [47] does not provide a certificate for these types of messages. Otherwise, the Routing Platform will encounter an error and crash. The Docker [49] images, available on Docker Hub [52] as part of the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit for the Routing Core, must be pulled for this purpose.

Important: To download certificates from Microsec [47], the module in the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit must have internet access. Therefore, some configurations must be made on the module, as shown in Chapter 5.2.1. Furthermore, both vehicleCAPTAIN development kits, which are used for sending and receiving, need to have the certificates installed on their modules.

To successfully enable V2X communication, the following files must be uploaded in the correct order:

1. GN Daemon Configuration, see Chapter 5.1.1
2. Canonical ID and Canonical Private Key
3. Certificate Request Config; do not forget to set the *CCMS_RequestEnable* field on true and use the SSPs from the vendor's certificates, see Chapter 5.1.1
4. PKI Register Config; fixed filename: "*ccms_pki_register_cfg.json*"
5. Certificates from Microsec
6. V2Xcast Configuration file, see Chapter 5.1.1

The following sections provide an overview of the purpose of these files and explain how they should be structured or how to download them.

Module Configurations: The following configurations on the module need to be set to download the certificates provided by Microsec [47] from their portal.

First, connect to the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit via Secure Shell (SSH), as shown in Source 5.11, and then execute the commands shown in Source 5.12. These commands configure iptables to enable internet access for the module by setting up Network Address Translation (NAT) and allowing traffic forwarding between the module's and external network interfaces.

```
ssh pi@{IP_ADDRESS_RASPI}
```

Src. 5.11: Connecting to vehicleCAPTAIN development kit via SSH.

```

sudo iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o {OUTBOUND_INTERFACE} -j MASQUERADE
sudo iptables -A FORWARD -m conntrack --ctstate RELATED,ESTABLISHED -j
    ↪ ACCEPT
sudo iptables -A FORWARD -i {INBOUND_INTERFACE} -o {OUTBOUND_INTERFACE} -j
    ↪ ACCEPT
sudo iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o {OUTBOUND_INTERFACE} -j MASQUERADE
sudo iptables -I DOCKER-USER 1-m conntrack --ctstate RELATED,ESTABLISHED -j
    ↪ ACCEPT
sudo iptables -I DOCKER-USER 2-i {INBOUND_INTERFACE} -o {
    ↪ OUTBOUND_INTERFACE} -j ACCEPT

```

Src. 5.12: Enable traffic forwarding.

After that, connect to the mPCI-E/M.2 module, intended to be a V2X module via SSH in the Raspberry Pi environment, as shown in Source 5.13.

```
ssh root@{IP_ADDRESS_MODULE}
```

Src. 5.13: Connecting to module via SSH.

Then, configure the `/etc/resolv.conf` file by adding the appropriate Domain Name System (DNS) server addresses. Modifying this file is necessary to configure the DNS servers for resolving domain names into IP addresses, ensuring proper network connectivity.

Canonical ID and Canonical Private Key: The canonical ID represents the permanent ID of the ITS-S and must be unique per the Long Term Certification Authority (LTCA), which is a security management entity that functions in an online mode [53].

A canonical ID needs to be generated, where the maximum length is 32 characters. A canonical private key is a standardized and consistent format of a private key used in a PKI to ensure it functions correctly across various systems and applications. Additionally, a public key is generated. The files need not be prepared if the canonical ID, the canonical private key, and the canonical public key are generated by `v2xcast_manager` [48], as shown in Source 5.14. For this command, choose a suitable string for the `CANONICAL_ID` for the device, but include a fixed prefix. The prefix is provided by the Microsec [47] Portal, as shown in Figure 5.11, but it needs to be converted to American Standard Code for Information Interchange (ASCII). The successful generation of the canonical ID, the canonical private key, and the canonical public key is shown in Figure 5.9.

```

./v2xcast_manager -m put {
    ↪ IP_ADDRESS_MODULE}/gen/canonical_keypair?{CANONICAL_ID}

```

Src. 5.14: Generating canonical ID and private key.

```

===== CA certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8
=====
===== HOME PKI certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8
=====

===== Canonical Info =====
canonical id        canonical private key status  canonical public key(uncompressed)
=====
[REDACTED] vehicleCAPTAIN006    settled              04 [REDACTED] 941f
=====

===== EE certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8            psid
=====

```

Fig. 5.9: Result after generating the canonical ID, private key, and public key.

Microsec: To download the certificates provided by Microsec [47], visit the Microsec Portal [54], as shown in Figure 5.10. First, download the AA and EA certificates provided by Microsec under the "CCMS PKI" section, specifically under "CA certificates". Next, navigate to "CCMS PKI" section, specifically under "Registered Devices" to add the two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits. To do this, click on the "Add new device..." button, which will open a popup window, as shown in Figure 5.11 and Figure 5.12.

V2X PKI
BY MICROSEC

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Organisation: Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH

Welcome to the Microsec V2X PKI Sandbox Portal!

This platform is designed to simplify and support your C-ITS and V2X testing and integration processes. Here, you can register your devices with our European CCMS Sandbox and our North American SCMS Sandbox, request test (EC/AT) certificates, and access various tools such as a COER decoder. To explore these features and more, use the menu on the left side of your screen.

Keep in mind that full access to the Sandbox Portal is granted only following Microsec's approval after your registration. For this, simply contact us at info@v2x-pki.com.

About the Microsec V2X PKI Sandbox!

The Microsec V2X PKI Sandbox is a test security framework designed to ensure the safety of vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication. It meets the requirements of the European C-ITS Security Credential Management System (CCMS) and the North American Security Credential Management System (SCMS). Within these environments, we utilise public key infrastructures (PKI) to ensure security by verifying the participants' permissions through the use of certificates.

The **Microsec V2X PKI CCMS Sandbox** solution has been developed to comply with various standards and specifications. These include the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IEEE)'s WAVE and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)'s ITS standards, such as:

- IEEE Std 1609.2 - IEEE Standard for Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE)
- ETSI TS 102 940 - ITS-S security (PKI) architecture and application groups
- ETSI TS 102 941 - Trust and Privacy Management
- ETSI TS 103 097 - Certificate and message structure definitions for C2CPKI

The **Microsec V2X PKI SCMS Sandbox** solution has been developed according to the standards and specifications required by the North American market, incorporating the following IEEE standards:

- IEEE Std 1609.2 - IEEE Standard for Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE)
- IEEE 1609.2.1 - IEEE Standard for Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE) Certificate Management Interfaces for End Entities

For more information, we encourage you to visit our website at <https://v2x-pki.com/>.

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PRIVACY NOTICE EN

Fig. 5.10: Microsec [47] V2X PKI Sandbox Portal.

As shown in Figure 5.11, the *Canonical ID* field in the portal must be filled in with the canonical ID set in Chapter 5.2.1 including the prefix, but it must be converted to hexadecimal. Additionally, the uncompressed key generated in Chapter 5.2.1, as shown in Figure 5.9 in the *canonical public key (uncompressed)* field, needs to be entered in the *compressed key* field of the Microsec [47] Portal. Then select the required *key type*, such as NistP256. The yellow arrows in the figure indicate the fields that must be filled out for this process.

As shown in Figure 5.12, the *AppPermissions* need to be defined, see Chapter 5.1.1, by providing the PSID and the SSP for the required certificates. The certificates, along with their PSID and SSP, must match those defined in the Certificate Request Config file, see Chapter 5.1.1. Then choose the *geographic validity* of the certificate. The yellow arrows in the figure indicate the fields that must be filled out for this work. Lastly, click on *save* to register the new device.

Add new device...

i Please make sure that the Canonical ID starts with the organization's prefix: {Prefix}

Canonical ID (HEX encoded) ↙ Readable name (optional) ↙

Compressed key (HEX encoded) ↙

Supported formats: RFC5480 SubjectPublicKeyInfo, 1609dot2 PublicVerificationKey, compact representation of an elliptic curve point (starts with 02/03/04)

Key type
NistP256

AppPermissions i

OBU DEFAULTS RSU DEFAULTS

SAVE CLOSE

Fig. 5.11: Add New Device (Part 1).

AppPermissions i

OBU DEFAULTS RSU DEFAULTS

PSID ↙ SSP ↙

0 0000

ADD... ↙

The geographic validity of the certificate i

Country

AUSTRIA ↙

SAVE CLOSE

Fig. 5.12: Add New Device (Part 2).

PKI Register Config: The PKI Register Config file must have the structure as shown in Source 5.15. The *Vendor* field should be filled in with the PKI vendor’s name. The *EA_URL* represents the EA’s Uniform Resource Locator (URL). The *AA_URL* corresponds to the AA’s URL. The *AppPermission* field specifies the app permissions in an enrollment certificate. The *PSID*, as shown in Chapter 3.1.4, must be set to 623, which stands for “secured certificate request.” The *SSP*, as detailed in Chapter 4.4, indicates the service-specific permissions [48].

To upload this file see Chapter 5.2.1.

```
{
  "PKI_Info":{
    "Vendor":"Microsec",
    "EA_URL":"http://{URL}/ecRequest",
    "AA_URL":"http://{URL}/atRequest"
  },
  "EC_Request":{
    "AppPermission":[
      {
        "PSID":623,
        "SSP":"{SSP}"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

Src. 5.15: Structure of PKI Register Config file.

Upload Bootstrap folder: Create a folder called *bootstrap_bundle* and copy the files, which are downloaded from the Portal in Chapter 5.2.1, into this folder, but rename them to *homepki-aa.cert*, *homepki-ea.cert*, and *homepki-rca.cert*. Also, copy the PKI Register Config file into the same folder.

In Source 5.16, the command to upload the files with bootstrap, is shown.

```
./v2xcast_manager -m put -b -path {PATH_TO_FOLDER} {
  ↪ IP_ADDRESS_MODULE}/upld/bootstrap
```

Src. 5.16: Bootstrap Upload.

Then, reconnect via SSH to the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit as shown in Source 5.11, and in this environment, connect to the module via SSH as shown in Source 5.13.

In the module, navigate to the directory */usr/bin* and execute the command shown in Source 5.17. The first parameter indicates the number of AT requests, which can be chosen from 1 to 5, and the second parameter specifies the interval time for the AT download, which can be selected from 1 to 168 hours [48]. After executing this command, the certificates should be uploaded to the module, as shown in Figure 5.13, which shows the successful upload.

```
./ccms_client {NUM_AT_REQ} {INTERVAL_TIME_AT_DOWNLOAD}
```

Src. 5.17: CCMS Client Download.

```

===== CA certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8
=====
===== HOME PKI certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8
=====
0_MicrosecTest-AA-2021_L0    Thu Oct 21 12:59:32 2021    Wed Oct 21 18:05:32 2026    [REDACTED]
MicrosecNistP256RootCA      Mon Oct 21 13:22:44 2019    Thu Oct 21 11:56:20 2027    [REDACTED]
0_MicrosecTest-EA-2021_L0    Thu Oct 21 12:52:00 2021    Wed Oct 21 17:58:00 2026    [REDACTED]
=====

===== Canonical Info =====
canonical id        canonical private key status    canonical public key(uncompressed)
=====
[REDACTED]device007    settled                        04 [REDACTED] 319:
=====

===== EE certificates =====
name                start time          end time            hashid8            psid
=====
at_4_20240903_100058    Tue Sep 3 10:00:58 2024    Tue Sep 10 10:00:58 2024    [REDACTED]        139
at_3_20240903_100058    Tue Sep 3 10:00:57 2024    Tue Sep 10 10:00:57 2024    [REDACTED]        138
at_2_20240903_100057    Tue Sep 3 10:00:57 2024    Tue Sep 10 10:00:57 2024    [REDACTED]        137
at_1_20240903_100056    Tue Sep 3 10:00:56 2024    Tue Sep 10 10:00:56 2024    [REDACTED]        37
at_5_20240903_100059    Tue Sep 3 10:00:59 2024    Tue Sep 10 10:00:59 2024    [REDACTED]        140
at_0_20240903_100055    Tue Sep 3 10:00:55 2024    Tue Sep 10 10:00:55 2024    [REDACTED]        36
=====

```

Fig. 5.13: Successful upload of certificates from Microsec [47].

5.2.2 Measurement Setup

See Chapter 5.1.2 for the necessary measurement setup.

5.2.3 Measurements

Figure 5.14 shows the Sender Example and Figure 5.15 shows the Receiver Example from the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5], demonstrating the successful transmission of secured CAMs with the certificates provided by Microsec [47]. In the figure, the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit on the left is sending the secured CAMs, while the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit on the right is successfully receiving them.

```

neubaueradm@INN80: i2:~$ docker exec -it cpp_sender-demo ./cppSender [IP_ADDRESS] 5555 2 1
main()
main(): connect ZMQ (tcp://[IP_ADDRESS]:5555)

main(): main loop

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- CAM --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #0

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- CAM --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #1

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- CAM --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #2

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- CAM --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #3

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- CAM --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #4

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- CAM --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #5

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- CAM --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #6

*** ** V2X Message Creation *** **
--- --- CAM --- ---
getGenerationDeltaTime(): not yet implemented - read comments in code
CAM created successfully with size 41
main(): sent msg #7

```

Fig. 5.14: Successful sender simulation with PKI certificates.

Figure 5.16 shows the result of successfully transmitting secured CAMs via the two vehicleCAP-TAIN development kits. This test was captured the same way as in Figure 5.8.

6 Discussion

This chapter aims to discuss and answer the three RQs formulated in Chapter 2. The following chapters will revisit these questions to highlight the main conclusions drawn from the corresponding sections of this thesis.

6.1 RQ1: Basic components of V2X

The first RQ, “What are the basic components of V2X?” is addressed in Chapter 3.1. This chapter identified several components required to establish V2X communication, such as OBUs in vehicles, RSUs in infrastructure, and a central or cloud server. These components are part of a C-ITS, which extends ITS. C-ITS enhances ITS by enabling vehicles to communicate directly with each other and the infrastructure. The communication within C-ITS depends on standards, such as those defined by ETSI, to ensure interoperability across different platforms and regions. This work focused specifically on European standards due to their relevance in the study region. Chapter 3.1.1 presents the various communication modes through which V2X operates, including (i) V2V, (ii) V2I, (iii) V2P, (iv) V2N, and (v) I2N, where each mode has a specific function in the V2X infrastructure. It is also important to consider how these modes affect the efficiency and safety of V2X systems. For example, each mode’s specific role in communication shows how complex it is to keep all parts of a V2X system working together. Additionally, we identified that V2X communication enables the transmission of V2X messages to exchange information with other ITS-Ss. These standardized messages are important for the system to work well in different areas and platforms. Complying with standards like those from ETSI is essential for V2X communication systems to be successful.

6.2 RQ2: Basic components of V2X Security

The second RQ, “What are the basic components of V2X Security?” is addressed in Chapter 4. This chapter outlines the elements necessary for securing communication in a V2X infrastructure. V2X security requirements can be divided into five parts: confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity, and non-repudiation, collectively known as CIAAN. In the EU, the ETSI ITS architecture is defined, which integrates the Security Layer into the four ITS processing layers: (i) Application Layer, (ii) Facilities Layer, (iii) Network & Transport, and (iv) Access Layer, as detailed in Chapter 3.1.3. The Security Layer includes Security Management Services and the Security Defense Layer. The combination of these layers provides security services to ensure secure V2X communication. The security services include authorization, certificate management, authentication, and more. Chapter 4.2 identifies various security threats that challenge a V2X infrastructure. Examples of security threats are spoofing, injecting false

message attacks, DoS attacks, eavesdropping attacks, replay attacks, and Sybil attacks. Each attack can be linked to the CIAAN principles. Chapter 4.3 discusses proactive and reactive security strategies to secure V2X communication. Proactive approaches are used to identify security challenges before they occur. This approach includes cryptography-based methods, like PKIs, physical security, and privacy preservation, and ensures authenticity and integrity by using security policies. In contrast, reactive approaches focus on detecting and responding to attacks. The main focus of this work was on the proactive method of PKIs. PKIs provide secure communication in V2X systems by securing the messages shared between components. They use cryptographic certificates to verify the identity of each component. Through the integration of PKIs, components in the V2X infrastructure can trust the data, even though it is not encrypted and visible to everyone. The sender's identity remains anonymous.

6.3 RQ3: Demonstration of security components in a V2X application

The third RQ, “How can the security components be demonstrated in a V2X application?” is addressed in Chapter 5. This chapter explores the integration of V2X security within a real-world application. This integration involves properly setting up the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit and uploading certificates provided by Unex [4] or a PKI to the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit. Two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits were used for the testing, one acting as OBU and one as RSU. The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] provides a framework for simulating scenarios, such as testing the effectiveness of configured security measures by using the Receiver Example and the Sender Example to send and receive V2X messages between the vehicleCAPTAIN development kits. In the absence of certificates for specific message types, the Routing Core of the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit crashes, and the code needs to be adjusted for the special test scenarios, but the results demonstrate that the secure message exchange is reliable under different conditions and effectively secures the communication between the two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits. Upgrading the Routing Core, which also upgrades the Unex V2Xcast[®] SDK from version 1.7 to 1.13, was necessary for several security reasons: (i) in version 1.7, the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit could only send secured CAMs and DENMs because the provided ETSI demo certificates were limited to these two message types, and while the upgrade to version 1.13 allowed the secure transmission of additional message types beyond these basics, some message types, like CPMs, which will be important for future applications, still cannot be sent securely; and (ii) in version 1.7 of Unex's V2Xcast[®] software, the CCMS client, which supports downloading and installing certificates from PKI vendors, was not supported. For this work, the QTSP Microsec [47] provided its PKI security solution. Microsec's portal only allows downloading certificates for certain message types and does not permit users to create or configure their own certificates.

7 Conclusion and Outlook

This paper explored the integration and demonstration of V2X security components within the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5]. The primary goal was to understand and implement the basic components of V2X communication and security, focusing on integrating secure V2X communication into a real-world application. The results show that the vehicleCAPTAIN development kit successfully secured V2X communication for various V2X message types. After upgrading the Routing Core's V2Xcast[®] software framework from version 1.7 to 1.13, additional message types were supported for transmission, and the integration of PKIs became possible. The system's reliability was successfully demonstrated by sending secured CAMs and DENMs between two vehicleCAPTAIN development kits, acting as OBU and RSU. Microsec's [47] PKI provided the necessary certificates, and their user-friendly portal ensured the messages were secure. However, there were limitations, such as the possibility of sending secure CPMs due to restrictions on message types by Unex [4] and Microsec [47].

The primary limitation during this work was the restriction to create or configure custom certificates within the PKI framework. This limitation prevented secure communication with specific message types, like CPMs, which are crucial for future V2X applications, as they enhance awareness and safety by allowing vehicles to share sensor data about non-V2X-equipped road users. Additionally, the Routing Core of the vehicleCAPTAIN crashes if certificates for specific message types are absent. Therefore the code has to be adjusted for the special test scenario of the PKI integration. Furthermore, this work was limited to hardware and software supplied by Unex [4] and the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5], which may not represent all possible V2X implementations.

Future work in this area could focus on providing additional V2X message types, testing with alternative PKI vendors, or creating more flexible certificate management services to create custom certificates. Furthermore, improvements to the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [5] could enhance its suitability across various V2X use cases.

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Table of Abbreviations

AA	Authorization Authority
ABE	Attribute-based Encryption
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AID	Application Identifier
API	Application Programming Interface
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
ASN1	Abstract Syntax Notation One
AT	Authorization Ticket
AV	Automated Vehicle
BS	Base Station
BSA	Basic Set of Applications
BTP	Basic Transport Protocol
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CA	Certification Authority
CA	Cooperative Awareness
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CCMS	Credential Management System
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CIA	Confidentiality Integrity Availability
CIAAN	Confidentiality Integrity Availability Authenticity Non-Repudiation
CP	Collective Perception
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CPOC	C-ITS Point of Contact
CTL	Trust List Information
DCC	Decentralized Congestion Control
DEN	Decentralized Environmental Notification
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DNS	Domain Name System
EA	Enrolment Authority
EC	Enrolment Credential
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FOSS	Free and Open-Source Software
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GHz	Gigahertz

GN	GeoNetworking
HLA	High-Level Architecture
HSM	Hardware Security Modules
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
I2N	Infrastructure-to-Network
IBC	Identity-based Cryptography
ID	Identifier
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IO	Input/Output
IP	Internet Protocol
IPC	Inter-Process Communication
IPv6	Internet Protocol Version 6
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
ITS-AID	Intelligent Transport System Application Identifier
ITS-S	ITS Station
ITSC	Intelligent Transport System Communications
ITSG5	Intelligent Transport Systems in the 5GHz band
IUMC	Inter-Unit Management Communication
IVI	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information
IVIM	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
LLC	Logical Link Control
LPWAN	Low-Pan Wide-Area Networks
LTCA	Long Term Certification Authority
MAC	Medium Access Control
MAPEM	MAP (topology) Extended Message
Mbp/s	Megabits per Second
MHz	Megahertz
MIB	Management Information Base
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NAT	Network Address Translation
OBU	Onboard unit
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PDU	Protocol Data Units
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PLS	Physical Layer Security
POP3	Post Office Protocol
POTI	Position and Time management
PSID	Provider Service Identifier
QTSP	Qualified Trust Service Provider
RLT	Road and Lane Topology
ROS	Robot Operating System
RQ	Research Question
RSU	Roadside Unit

RX	Reception
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDU	Service Data Unit
SIB	Security Information Base
SOM	System-on-Module
SPATEM	Signal Phase and Timing Extended Message
SREM	Signal Request Extended Message
SSCM	Security Credential Management System
SSEM	Signal request Status Extended Message
SSH	Secure Shell
SSP	Service Specific Permissions
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TLC	Traffic Light Control
TLM	Traffic Light Maneuver
TTP	Trusted Third Party
TX	Transmission
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
USA	United States of America
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle-to-Network
V2P	Vehicle-to-Person/Pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
vehicleCAPTAIN	Vehicle Communication Platform to Anything
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
ZMQ	Zero Message Queueing

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